

FATTY ACIDS AND GLYCERIDES OF THE OIL FROM SAPOTA SEEDS (*ACHRAS SAPOTA*).

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The seeds of *Acharas sapota* contain about 10% of a liquid fat. The component fatty acids and the glycerides of the oil have been determined. The component fatty acids of the oil are lauric acid (1.6%), myristic acid (6.2%), palmitic acid (12.6%), stearic acid (12.0%), oleic acid (66.2%) and linoleic acid (1.4%). The component glycerides have been calculated to be oleopalmitostearin (5%), dioleomyrestin (23%), dioleopalmitin (36%), dioleostearin (28%), triolein (5%) with another 3% of disaturated mono-olein in which probably the saturated acids are lauric, myristic and a little of palmitic acids.

Sapota (*Achras sapota*) belongs to the natural order of sapotaceæ. The evergreen trees of Sapotas are grown extensively in the southern parts of India. It gives a delicious, edible fruit. Each fruit contains two or three seeds, weighing about 0.5 g. The seeds are covered with a hard dark coloured shell, which can be easily removed, if they are fully dried. The seeds are a waste material. They have kernels inside the hard shell, which comprises 50% of the seed and contains 20% of liquid fat. Although the percentage of oil in the seed is low, it may be possible to extract the oil and utilise it for commercial purpose, as the seeds can be obtained very cheap. The present investigation on the physical and chemical constants of the oil, component fatty acids and the component glycerides was taken up with a view firstly to make these data available for commercial utilisation of the oil and secondly to put forward some more evidence towards the general characteristics of the fats from fruit-coated seeds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The seeds, obtained from the local sapota fruits, were washed, cleaned and dried. 2.5 Kg. of the seeds, crushed to 24 mesh, gave 252 g. of a light coloured oil, when extracted with carbon tetrachloride. The chemical and physical constants are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Sp. gr. at 31°	0.8725	Acid value (as % oleic acid)	8.94
Refrac. index at 31°	1.463	Reichert-Meissel value (0.5 g. of oil)	2.8
Sapon. value	205.4	Hehner value	92.6
Iodine value (Wij's)	59.8	Non-saponifiables	1.8

Component Fatty Acids.

The oil was saponified and the non-saponinables were extracted from the soap. The mixed acids liberated from the soap were resolved into solid and liquid acids by Twitchel's lead salt and alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). Methyl esters from these acids were fractionally distilled at 0.2 mm. pressure as given below.

TABLE II.

	Wt.	%.	Sapon. equiv.	Iodine No.
Oil	170 g.	—	273.1	59.8
Mixed acids	154	91.8	274.7	60.99
(S) Solid acids	97.4	64.9	263.8	46.88
(L) Liquid acids	52.7	35.1	283.2	89.76
(S) Methyl ester	...	...	276.4	45.46
(L) Methyl ester	...	...	296.8	87.34

TABLE IIIA.

Fractionation of esters.

Solid esters (S).

Fractions.	B. p.	Wt.	Sapon. equiv.	Iodine value.
S ₁	105-137°	3.4 g.	235.0	5.9
S ₂	130-132	4.3	242.3	8.7
S ₃	132	4.0	262.5	18.9
S ₄	134	5.8	279.9	27.1
S ₅	135	6.7	285.7	35.6
S ₆	136	15.3	286.3	44.2
S ₇	137-138°	17.5	291.6	58.3
S ₈	138	10.6	297.7	65.1
S ₉	138-140°	11.0	294.1	53.4
Residue	...	8.6	296.4	64.2
Total		<u>87.2</u>		

TABLE IIIB.

Liquid esters (L)				
Fractions.	B. p.	Wt.	Sapon. equiv.	Iodine value
L ₁	138-140°	2.8 g.	285.9	85.52
L ₂	142	8.1	295.0	89.93
L ₃	142-145°	5.2	294.8	89.96
L ₄	145	6.7	294.1	94.71
L ₅	155	3.8	294.4	96.03
Residue	—	3.4	294.6	81.77
		30.0		

The individual acids were identified from these fractions by their mixed melting point with authentic samples. The unsaturated acids were identified by their oxidation products with alkaline permanganate in cold (Lapworth and Mottram, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1698).

From L₁, lauric acid melting at 43° either alone or mixed pure lauric acid was obtained by petrol ether extraction of the oxidation product. Myristic acid (m.p. 53°), palmitic acid (m.p. 62°) and stearic acid (m.p. 70°) were identified from the different fractions of the solid esters.

Dihydroxystearic acid, melting at 130° either alone are mixed with pure $\Delta^{9:10}$ -dihydroxystearic acid and two tetrahydroxy acids, one melting at 154° (most soluble in hot water) and the other melting at 174° (least soluble in hot water) were identified from the oxidation products of the various liquid fractions.

From these observations the component fatty acids have been calculated as given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Acids.	Solid. 64.9 %	Liquid. 35.1 %	Total. % by wt.	Mol. %
Lauric acid	0.4	1.2	1.6	2.2
Myristic acid	2.7	3.5	6.2	7.4
Palmitic acid	10.4	2.2	12.6	13.7
Stearic acid	11.8	0.2	12.0	11.0
Oleic acid	39.6	26.6	66.2	64.2
Linoleic acid	—	1.4	1.4	1.5

The Component Glycerides.

Fully Saturated Glyceride.—Neutral oil (100 g.) (free acids were removed by washing the oil with sodium carbonate solution) was oxidised repeatedly with powdered potassium permanganate in acetone (Armstrong and Hilditch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 22, 447). In the end it gave 0.4 g of a neutral product, which was found to be non-saponifiable. This proves the absence of any fully saturated glyceride.

Separation of the Glycerides by Acetone.—Neutral oil (300 g.) was systematically crystallised from acetone at 0° and 14.5 g. of a least soluble fraction were obtained. The component fatty acids of both the fractions, less soluble (A) and more soluble (B) were determined by ester fractionations.

TABLE V.

	(A).	(B).	Total.
Weight (g.)	14.5	285.5	300.0
Sap. equivalent	273.0	275	274.9
Iodine value	29.5	61.4	60.1
% on total oil + non-sap.	4.6	95.4	—
% on glyceride	4.7	95.3	—
Mol. per cent.	4.8	95.2	—

TABLE VI.

	Component acids (weight %.)			Mol % of component acids.		
	A. (4.7%)	B. (95.3%)	Mean.	A. (4.8%)	B. (95.2%)	Mean.
Myristic acid	Trace	8.1	7.7	—	9.9	9.4
Palmitic acid	33.8	11.5	12.5	34.2	12.7	13.8
Stearic acid	33.0	10.1	11.2	32.8	9.7	10.8
Oleic acid	33.2	68.7	67.1	33.0	65.0	64.5
Linoleic acid	—	1.6	1.5	—	1.6	1.5

Myristic acid recorded here contains a small amount of lauric acid. These component acids agree within experimental limits with those determined directly from the oil.

Tri-C₁₈-glyceride.—Tristearin is not very much soluble in ether at a low temperature. It has been found that it can be quantitatively crystallised from ether at 0°.

In order to find out the quantity of tri-C₁₈-glycerides in this oil, fraction "B" was fully hydrogenated till the iodine value was nearly nil (1·8) and the hydrogenated product was systematically crystallised from ether. It gave 34·2% (mol.) or 34·5% by weight of tristearin, m. p. 71° and equivalent 296·8.

As the fraction "A" was obtained in small quantity it could not be subjected to the similar procedure as B. From the component fatty acids, it has been taken to be oleo-palmitostearin.

The component glycerides of the oil have been calculated from the above observations and given in the Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Molecular % of the acids in fractions A and B.

	A (4·8 %).	B (95·2 %).	Total (100).
Myristic acid	Trace	9·4	9·4
Palmitic acid	1·7	12·1	13·8
Stearic acid	1·6	9·2	10·8
Oleic acid	1·6	62·9	64·5
Linoleic acid	—	1·5	1·5

TABLE VIII.

Estimated % of glycerides in the oil.

	In fraction A. (4·8 %)	In fraction B. (95·2 %)	Total (100)
A Fully saturated glycerides	Nil	Nil	Nil
B. Tri-C ₁₈ -glycerides	—	32·8	32·8
C. Di-saturated-olein			
Oleo distearin	—	Nil	Nil
Oleo-palmitostearin	4·8	—	4·8
Oleo-di-palmitin	Nil	—	Nil

TABLE VIII (contd.).

	In fraction A.	In fraction B.	Total.
*Oleo myristo-palmitin or oleo-myristolaurin	—	3.0	3.0
Mono-saturated di-olein			
Di-oleo-stearin	—	27.8	27.8
Di-oleopalmitin	—	36.8	36.6
Di-oleomyristin		22.8	22.8
Tri-unsaturated glycerides			
Tri-olein	—	5	5

Myristic acid recorded here contains the small quantity of lauric acid oleic acid and a little of linoleic acid.

* This 3 % cent. of di saturated-olein could not be oleo-palmitostearin, which will remain in the acetone-insoluble portion. The saturated acids in this glyceride could be only lower acids like myristic, lauric and a little palmitic acid.

In round figures the component glycerides of sapota seed oil may be given as follows : oleo-palmitostearin (5%), di-oleostearin (28%), di-oleopalmitin (36%), di-oleomyristin (23%), tri-olein (about 5%) and about 3% of a di-saturated-mono-olein glycerides in which the saturated acids are myristic, lauric and palmitic acids.

The oil contains no fully saturated glycerides. The general glyceride structure of this oil agrees fairly well with the other fats of the *sapotaceæ* seeds. Fully saturated glycerides, which have been found in other *sapotaceæ* fats, are absent in this oil, probably because the percentage of saturated acids is rather low.

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